

**NOVEL NICKEL ALUMINATE-DERIVED CATALYSTS
SUPPORTED ON CERIA AND CERIA ZIRCONIA
FOR PARTIAL OXIDATION OF METHANE**

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Abstract

In this work novel nickel catalysts based on nickel aluminate deposited on ceria-based supports (CeO_2 and $\text{Ce}_{0.13}\text{Zr}_{0.87}\text{O}_2$) were investigated for the partial oxidation of methane. The good catalytic behaviour of the CeO_2 -based sample under moderate ($38400 \text{ mL CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and stoichiometric feed) and severe ($60000 \text{ mL CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, an O/C molar ratio of 0.8 and prolonged time on stream (30 h)) reaction conditions was mainly assigned to the small particle size (about 10 nm) that was achieved after the high-temperature reduction of the spinel and its notable redox properties. CeAlO_3 formation was found to play a negative effect on the catalytic performance, which was more pronounced for the $\text{Ce}_{0.13}\text{Zr}_{0.87}\text{O}_2$ supported catalyst. This negative impact could be controlled by the introduction of La_2O_3 since this promoter reacted with alumina to give LaAlO_3 instead of CeAlO_3 and favoured carbon gasification in the vicinity of nickel particles.

Keywords: nickel aluminate, methane partial oxidation, Ce-based supports, cerium aluminate, coke

1. Introduction

The crucial role of hydrogen as a clean fuel for meeting the future demands of energy is clearly accepted by both governments and industry. Although the production of H₂ should be ideally based on renewable hydrocarbons or water, fossil fuels processed by catalytic reforming technologies can still provide a reliable path in the near/mid-term.¹ Owing to its abundance, high H/C molar ratio and already available distribution infrastructure natural gas (methane) is a very attractive feedstock. From an operational point of view partial oxidation of methane is considerably simpler than steam reforming. In spite of the fact that the yield of hydrogen is comparatively lower, the energy requirements are less intensive due to the mild exothermicity of the reaction and no water is needed.

Nickel catalysts with loadings in the 5-20wt.% range are widely recognised as viable alternatives to noble metals (mainly rhodium catalysts). However, the conversion of methane is often limited by carbon deposition due to methane decomposition and/or CO disproportionation. The use of reducible oxides, such as ceria-based materials (CeO₂ or Ce_xZr_{1-x}O₂), has been shown to notably enhance the performance of nickel in methane reforming reactions. The promotion of both activity and stability of Ni/Ce_xZr_{1-x}O₂ catalysts has been generally associated with a large amount of oxygen vacancies in the vicinity of nickel particles.² Hence, this great ability to transfer active oxygen species in turn results in keeping the metal free of carbon species and a higher activity in comparison with nickel catalysts supported on alumina or zirconia.³ In fact, the usage of CeO₂ or Ce_xZr_{1-x}O₂ in Ni/Al₂O₃ catalytic systems has been successfully employed for a variety of reforming applications including steam reforming of ethane and propane⁴, dry reforming of methane⁵ and autothermal reforming of methane.⁶ The Ce/Al molar ratio of these catalysts is in the 0.01-0.08 range.

The preparation of supported nickel catalysts including Ni/Ce_xZr_{1-x}O₂ is based on nickel oxide (NiO) as catalytic precursor that subsequently is reduced to obtain metallic nickel as active phase. The temperature selected for reduction is influenced by the reforming temperature (usually higher than 650 °C when running at a volume hourly space velocity (VHSV) higher than 10000 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹). At these temperatures nickel sintering can negatively impact the behaviour of the catalyst. As an alternative to nickel oxide, nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄) has been proposed as an interesting catalytic precursor that provides highly dispersed metallic nickel crystallites on alumina after a proper reduction at relatively high temperatures (> 825 °C).⁷ In this sense recent works from our group have evidenced the good reforming performance of the bulk spinel or alumina supported spinels prepared by precipitation in the steam reforming of methane, isooctane and *n*-tetradecane.⁸⁻¹¹

On the basis of this background it would be of interest to analyse the behaviour of NiAl₂O₄ supported either on ceria or Ce_xZr_{1-x}O₂ for partial oxidation of methane. Particularly, CeO₂ and Ce_{0.13}Zr_{0.87}O₂ oxides will be investigated as supports. The potential of these new catalytic systems will be examined at constant temperature (700 °C) at a VHSV varying between 38400 and 60000 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ and an O/C molar ratio between 0.8 and 1. Furthermore, the viability of NiAl₂O₄ as catalytic precursor for metallic nickel will be addressed by comparatively analysing the performance of the corresponding supported NiO counterparts.

2. Experimental

2.1. Catalysts preparation

Support materials employed in this study were CeO₂ (28 m² g⁻¹, Rhodia) and CZ (Ce_{0.13}Zr_{0.87}O₂, 24 m² g⁻¹, Mel Chemicals), which were previously calcined at 850 °C for 8 h to obtain stable samples. Two set of nickel catalysts were prepared by varying the

nickel precursor (NiAl_2O_4 or NiO). Hence, the catalysts denoted as NiAl-CeO_2 and NiAl-CZ were prepared by precipitation of nickel aluminate. The process was conducted by the drop-by-drop addition under constant stirring of a 0.6 M solution of NH_4OH into an aqueous slurry of a mixture of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with a Ni/Al molar ratio of 0.50 and the corresponding support. The temperature was kept at 25 °C during the precipitation and the pH was set at 8. Afterwards, the samples were aged for 30 minutes before being filtered and washed with hot deionised water. As a reference a NiAl_2O_4 bulk catalyst (NiAl) was prepared following the same route. On the other hand, the catalysts labelled as NiO-CeO_2 and NiO-CZ were similarly synthesized but the selected nickel phase was NiO . In this case only nickel acetate was employed for synthesis.

The nominal Ni loading was fixed at 14wt.% for all samples. The catalysts were dried at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . This last step led to the formation of nickel aluminate or nickel oxide. As a reference reforming catalyst, a commercial $\text{Rh-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample was used (1% $\text{Rh-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, 132 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, Alfa Aesar). This sample was calcined at 700 °C for 4 h.

2.2. Catalyst characterisation

The calcined oxides were characterised by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES), N_2 physisorption at -196 °C, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), temperature-programmed reduction with hydrogen (H_2 -TPR) and successive H_2 -TPR/ O_2 -TPO/ H_2 -TPR cycles while the freshly reduced catalysts were analysed by N_2 physisorption, XRD and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). On the other hand, the post-run samples were studied by BET measurements, XRD, Raman spectroscopy, TEM and dynamic thermogravimetry coupled to mass spectrometry (TGA-

MS). The experimental details of each analytical technique are thoroughly described in the Supporting Information section.

2.3. *Catalytic activity*

Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor (Microactivity modular laboratory system provided by PID Eng&Tech S.L.) operated at atmospheric pressure and fully monitored by computer. The reactor was made of stainless steel with an internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm, in which the temperature was controlled with a thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.125 g of catalyst in powdered form (0.3-0.5 mm) was loaded. The catalyst bed was diluted with inert quartz (0.875 g, 1-1.25 mm) in order to avoid hot spot formation or temperature gradients. The partial oxidation of methane was studied with two different compositions of a feed gas mixture of CH₄ and O₂ balanced with N₂, with a total flow rate of 800 mL min⁻¹ and at a constant temperature of 700 °C:

- i) 10%CH₄ and 5%O₂ (80 mL CH₄ min⁻¹, 38400 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹, O/C=1, 3 h)
- ii) 15.6%CH₄ and 6.3%O₂ (125 mL CH₄ min⁻¹, 60000 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹, O/C=0.8, 30 h)

Prior to the reaction, the nickel catalysts were activated in situ by reduction with 5%H₂/N₂ at 850 °C for 2 h whereas the rhodium catalyst was reduced at 700 °C. Feed and effluent streams were analysed online by a MicroGC (Agilent 3000) equipped with a TCD detector. Two columns, Molecular Sieve 5A and Plot U, were used in a series/bypass arrangement for the complete separation of H₂, N₂, O₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂. A cold trap at the outlet of the reactor was used to condense out any water from the product gas stream. On the basis of the molar flow at the inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and product yields were calculated, according to the following equations:

$$X_{\text{CH}_4}, \% = \frac{F_{\text{CO, out}} + F_{\text{CO}_2, \text{out}}}{F_{\text{CH}_4, \text{in}}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{F_{\text{H}_2, \text{out}}}{2 \cdot F_{\text{CH}_4, \text{in}}} \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{\text{CO}} = \frac{F_{\text{CO, out}}}{F_{\text{CH}_4, \text{in}}} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{F_{\text{CO}_2, \text{out}}}{F_{\text{CH}_4, \text{in}}} \quad (4)$$

The thermodynamic data were calculated via the HSC Chemistry software package by the GIBBS programme using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimisation Method. In addition to solid carbon, the following gaseous substances were considered: CH₄, O₂, N₂, CO, CO₂, H₂ and H₂O.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Characterisation of the samples

The nickel content of the catalysts was determined by ICP-AES and it was verified to be relatively close to the nominal values (14wt.% for the supported samples and 33wt.% for the bulk NiAl catalyst) (Table 1). The structural properties were characterised by XRD using JCPDS files as reference. The XRD spectra for the calcined catalysts are shown in Figure 1 (samples (a)). In the case of the supported NiAl catalysts the set of diffraction peaks at $2\theta=37.1^\circ$, 45.1° , 59.3° and 65.7° , assignable to the stoichiometric nickel aluminate phase (JCPDS 78-1601), was clearly observed.¹¹ Interestingly, peaks related to NiO species were not found. The exclusive formation of the spinel with a stoichiometric composition (Ni/Al=1/2) was also observed for the bulk sample. These results pointed out the efficiency

of the precipitation synthesis route to produce samples with a predominant presence of NiAl_2O_4 phase.^{8,11} Expectedly the patterns of the catalysts prepared by the precipitation of nickel acetate revealed that the nickel phase was nickel oxide (JCPDS 89-7131), in view of the intense diffraction peaks located at $2\theta=37.4^\circ$, 43.4° and 63.0° . Obviously the patterns of both sets of samples gave the characteristic reflections of the used ceria-based supports as well. Thus, NiAl-CZ and NiO-CZ catalysts exhibited diffraction peaks corresponding to the tetragonal structure of the ceria-zirconia mixed oxide with a low Ce/Zr molar ratio (JCPDS 88-2397) whereas NiAl-CeO₂ and NiO-CeO₂ samples showed diffraction signals related to the cubic structure of the ceria (JCPDS 89-8436).

Figure 1

The nature of the nickel species at the surface level was analysed by XPS. Figure 2 shows the photoemission peak of Ni 2p_{3/2} for supported NiAl and NiO catalysts. In the case of NiAl-CZ and NiAl-CeO₂, the apparent symmetry of the Ni 2p_{3/2} signals suggested the presence of a single homogeneous phase. In fact, the comparison between their Ni 2p_{3/2} positions (856.4 eV for NiAl-CZ and 856.1 eV for NiAl-CeO₂) and the theoretical binding energy for NiAl₂O₄ (856.0 eV) corroborated that the near-surfaces were mainly composed of nickel aluminate structure.^{12,13} By contrast, the XPS curves in the Ni 2p_{3/2} region for the supported NiO catalysts displayed much broader and less symmetric peaks. On the basis of this observation, the nickel environment was deconvoluted in two peaks. Hence, the first peak with a binding energy around 854.0 eV was attributed to NiO with a weak interaction with the support. The second feature at a higher binding energy (855.6-856.0 eV) corresponded to NiO with a stronger interaction with the support.^{11,14}

Figure 2

The XRD patterns of the reduced catalysts are also included in Figure 1 (samples (b)). This analysis confirmed that the reduction process used prior to reaction runs (850 °C/2 h) was adequate to achieve the complete reduction of nickel precursors for both supported NiAl and NiO samples. Indeed, the NiAl-CZ and NiAl-CeO₂ catalysts contained metallic nickel (JCPDS 89-7128, 2θ=44.7°, 51.9° and 76.5°), alumina (JCPDS 79-1558, 2θ=45.7° and 66.6°) (both phases associated with the conversion of the spinel into Ni/Al₂O₃) and the corresponding support. It must be pointed out that the reduction of NiAl-CeO₂ was also accompanied by the formation of CeAlO₃ (2CeO₂+Al₂O₃+H₂→2CeAlO₃+H₂O).^{15,16} The generation of cerium aluminate (JCPDS 28-0260, 2θ=23.5°, 33.6°, 41.6°, 48.3°, 54.4° and 60.2°) implied that a fraction of cerium atoms was fixed as stable Ce³⁺ cations and therefore it was no longer involved in the Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ redox cycle. In fact, diffraction lines of alumina were not clearly identified owing to the formation of this phase, thereby suggesting a favoured reaction of CeO₂ and Al₂O₃ during the activation step. Conversely, CeAlO₃ was not apparently observed in the pattern of the reduced NiAl-CZ probably due to the lower amount of cerium of the CZ support. This finding was in agreement with the presence of the alumina phase at 2θ=45.7° and 66.6°. On the other hand, the nickel precursor of supported NiO samples was completely reduced into metallic nickel as well.

The physical properties of the supports and the nickel catalysts were examined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements. All the samples exhibited IV-type isotherms (not shown), thus displaying a hysteresis loop associated with the presence of mesoporous structure.¹⁷ Table 1 summarises the specific surface area, pore volume and average pore size. When compared with the BET surface area of the bare supports (24 m² g⁻¹ for CZ and 28 m² g⁻¹ for CeO₂) both calcined supported NiAl samples had a markedly larger value

(about 52-54 m² g⁻¹). This was attributed to the contribution of the high area of the nickel spinel. Note that the surface area of the bulk nickel aluminate was about 90 m² g⁻¹. In contrast, the calcined NiO catalysts underwent a considerable loss of surface area (12 m² g⁻¹ for NiO-CZ and 8 m² g⁻¹ for NiO-CeO₂), mainly due to the low surface of nickel oxide (< 3 m² g⁻¹) and the blocking of the pores. In view of these results it could be stated that the use of NiAl₂O₄ as nickel precursor provided catalysts with a noticeably higher surface area. It should be highlighted that the surface area was slightly decreased (from 52-54 m² g⁻¹ to 48 m² g⁻¹) after activation by reduction.

Table 1

H₂-TPR experiments were carried out in order to identify the nickel phases present in each catalyst and analyse their influence on the reducibility of the Ce-based supports. For a better understanding of the profiles of the supported catalysts the redox behaviour of the bare supports (CeO₂ and CZ) and the bulk nickel phases (NiAl₂O₄ and NiO) were firstly studied (Figure 3). Starting with the pure ceria support, two uptakes were distinguished; the first one, located in the 300-450 °C range, was linked to the reduction of the uppermost layers of Ce⁴⁺ and the second one, located at temperatures above 600 °C, belonged to the reduction of bulk ceria, which required temperatures as high as 900 °C.^{15,18} Note that the contribution of the reducible surface species was very small, probably due to the high temperature used for thermal stabilisation (850 °C).¹⁹ The experimental H₂ consumption was 1.63 mmol g⁻¹ that corresponded to a degree of reduction of 56%. As for the pure CZ mixed oxide, only one reduction feature was observed with a peak temperature at around 625 °C. The presence of a single peak at the low temperature region suggested that the addition of ZrO₂ promoted the reduction of the bulk ceria. This was attributed to an improvement of the oxygen anion mobility induced by the insertion of ZrO₂ into the CeO₂

lattice.²⁰⁻²² As a result a complete reduction of the cerium atoms present in the oxide was attained (0.49 mmol H₂ g⁻¹). The reduction profile of pure bulk nickel aluminate was characterised by a consumption at 450 °C corresponding to NiO not properly incorporated into the crystalline structure of the spinel. These species could be considered as free nickel oxide species (α -type NiO). At higher temperatures (500-900 °C) a much more intense feature was observed with two reduction peaks at 690 and 780 °C. The signal at the lower temperature was probably due to reduction of the surface of the spinel and/or the reduction of spinel with a substoichiometric phase (β -type NiO) while the high-temperature peak was related to the reduction of the highly stabilised nickel aluminate structure (γ -type NiO).¹⁵ Conversely, the reduction profile of bulk NiO was expectedly dominated by the presence of easily reducible NiO species (α -type NiO), whose reduction temperature was centred at 450 °C.

Next the reducibility of the supported NiAl and NiO catalysts will be discussed. The quantitative analysis of the profiles (Table 2) revealed that all catalysts presented a H₂ consumption above the corresponding theoretical value necessary to reduce just the nickel present. Taking into consideration that Ni²⁺ species (either as NiAl₂O₄ or NiO) were completely reduced into metallic nickel as confirmed by XRD, it seemed clear that the ceria-based supports were also reduced during the analysis. Then, the hydrogen consumption referred to Ce⁴⁺ and the degree of reducibility of the support were estimated (Table 2). Thus, the overall H₂ uptake related to ceria in the NiAl-CeO₂ sample was 1.03 mmol H₂ g⁻¹ while the amount of H₂ connected to the reduction of the mixed oxide in the NiAl-CZ sample was 0.29 mmol H₂ g⁻¹. These measured quantities indicated that the

degree of reducibility of the supports were 60 and 100%, respectively. These values were very close to those obtained for the bare oxides.

Figure 3

Table 2

The shape of the TPR curves corresponding to the supported NiAl catalysts was very similar to that of the bulk nickel aluminate (Figure 4). After deconvolution four H₂ uptakes could be defined. The features located at 350-450, 700 and 800 °C were associated with the reduction of α -, β - and γ -type NiO species, respectively. Note that the definition of these contributions was made in such a way that the accumulative area coincided with the stoichiometric consumption of nickel species in relation to the overall reduction of the catalysts. The remaining fourth feature was assumed to correspond to the reduction of the support, at about 850 °C for the NiAl-CeO₂ sample and 540 °C for the NiAl-CZ catalyst. It is noteworthy that the reduction of the mixed oxide in the NiAl-CZ sample was shifted to lower temperatures with respect to the blank oxide (625 °C). This promotion was presumably due to the relatively high surface Ni/Ce molar ratio (5.5 as estimated by XPS), which could evidence a catalytically favoured reduction by nickel, in comparison with that of the CeO₂-supported sample (0.6).

Figure 4

As aforementioned of the creation of a layer of alumina on the surface of the ceria-based supports involved the formation of CeAlO₃ at high temperatures in the presence of hydrogen, by diffusion of Al³⁺ in the partially reduced CeO₂ lattice ($2\text{CeO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CeAlO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$). This was confirmed for the freshly reduced NiAl-CeO₂ catalyst by XRD (Figure 1). By contrast, the XRD profile of the freshly reduced

NiAl-CZ sample did not reveal a noticeable generation of CeAlO₃, probably due to its comparatively lower cerium content. However, a distinct H₂ consumption associated with the formation of this phase could not be clearly identified in the H₂-TPR profile since it surely overlapped with the various reduction processes that occur at high temperatures, this is to say, the reduction of γ -NiO species and/or the reduction of the bulk of the ceria in the NiAl-CeO₂ sample. Note that the observed H₂ uptake at high temperatures occurs at 850 °C, noticeably higher than 725 °C of the bare support. This consumption probably corresponds to the formation of cerium aluminate. Owing to the fact that CeAlO₃ may significantly inhibit the redox ability of the catalyst, an attempt was made to quantify the relative amount of this phase formed during the reduction step of the calcined catalytic precursors by comparing the H₂ uptake of the samples when submitted to a single H₂-TPR(950 °C) run and when submitted to a H₂-TPR(950 °C)/O₂-TPO(550 °C)/H₂-TPR(950 °C) cycle. The relative difference in H₂ uptake could be thus taken as an indication of the presence of this phase. It should be pointed out that during the O₂-TPO(550 °C) step all the nickel present in the samples was reoxidised to NiO. This was experimentally verified for the freshly reduced bulk NiAl sample. Thus, after oxidation at 550 °C a second TPR run (not shown) confirmed an H₂ uptake located at about 350 °C, which is typical of the reduction of NiO. Furthermore, the measured amount of H₂ corresponded to the nickel loading of the sample. On the other hand, on the basis of the findings reported by Prakash et al.²³ it was assumed that the eventually formed CeAlO₃ during the first H₂-TPR(950 °C) run was stable at 550 °C in an oxidative atmosphere. Furthermore, with the aim of ruling out the possible influence of an eventual sintering of the support during the first TPR that could reduce the hydrogen uptake in the consecutive TPR, the blank ceria-based supports were subjected to

the same TPR-TPO-TPR cycle. In this way, obtained data verified that the H₂ consumption in both TPR runs were identical. Results shown in Table 2 indicated that the formation of CeAlO₃ was appreciable in both NiAl supported catalysts but more marked in the case of the NiAl-CeO₂ sample (35% in comparison with 13% found for NiAl-CZ). Nevertheless, due to the larger Ce content of CeO₂ with respect to the CZ oxide, the amount of Ce⁴⁺ involved in the reversible Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ cycle was still larger in the NiAl-CeO₂ catalyst, with an H₂ uptake of 0.66 mmol H₂ g⁻¹ (0.25 mmol H₂ g⁻¹ for NiAl-CZ).

Moreover, in order to confirm the presence of CeAlO₃ on the catalyst surface, both calcined and reduced nickel catalysts were further characterised by XPS. For this purpose, the Ce 3d region was deeply analysed. According to the literature the Ce 3d spectrum is composed of five spin orbit doublets due to the multiplets, 3/2 (u) and 5/2 (v).^{24,25} These ten contributions could be distinguished depending on the oxidation state of cerium; hence, u/v, u''/v'', u'''/v''' are assigned to Ce⁴⁺ and u₀/v₀ and u'/v' are attributed to Ce³⁺. Based on this classification, the fitting of the Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ bands of the samples was performed (Figure 5) and the corresponding percentage area of each state was quantified. In this way, the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ ratios of the supported NiAl catalysts before and after high-temperature reduction were determined (Table S1). From these ratios it was thus possible to estimate the degree of conversion of Ce⁴⁺ species into cerium aluminate at the surface of the reduced samples. While assuming that the increased formation of Ce³⁺ in the reduced samples was only because of the appearance of CeAlO₃, it was found that the percentage of cerium atoms transformed into CeAlO₃ after reduction at high temperatures was about 3% for NiAl-CeO₂ and 11% for NiAl-CZ. When compared with the results obtained from the bulk analysis, it seemed that the CeAlO₃ formation massively occurred in the bulk of the CeO₂-based catalyst cerium oxide in view of the low concentration of this phase at the surface. In

the case of the mixed oxide supported catalyst the concentration of CeAlO₃ was roughly similar as estimated from both XPS and H₂-TPR/O₂-TPO/H₂-TPR analysis.

Figure 5

As for the supported NiO samples, the overall reducibility of the support was negatively affected by the presence of NiO, with a degree of reducibility of 27 and 54% for NiO-CeO₂ and NiO-CZ, respectively (Table 2). The observed unpromoted reducibility was assigned to the noticeably large nickel crystallites (100-150 nm as estimated later on by XRD) formed during reduction, which were not active for enhancing the redox properties of the support. The reduction profile of the NiO-CZ sample exhibited two main uptakes located at 380 and 550 °C. After deconvolution up to four signals could be noticed. The first three peaks at 385, 440 and 540 °C suggested the presence of different α -type NiO species with varying interaction with the support.²⁶ The hydrogen uptake observed at 650 °C was attributed to the partial reduction of the ceria zirconia mixed oxide. On the contrary, the trace of NiO-CeO₂ was quite simpler with a clear distinction between the reduction of α -type NiO species (with a peak reduction temperature at 385 °C) and the reduction of the bulk of ceria support (with a peak temperature at 850 °C).²⁷

The mean Ni particle size of the reduced supported nickel catalysts was estimated by XRD from the Ni (200) signal at $2\theta=51.7^\circ$. It was noticed that the metallic crystallite size of supported NiO catalysts was considerably large, around 100 nm and 150 nm for NiO-CeO₂ and NiO-CZ catalysts, respectively. By contrast, the size for NiAl-CZ was about 6 nm. In the case of NiAl-CeO₂ the diffraction lines were very weak and the estimation was therefore not possible. This suggested the existence of crystallites smaller than 5 nm. Hence, when using NiAl₂O₄ as precursor the average size of metallic nickel was about one

order of magnitude lower than their NiO-based counterparts. The supported NiAl catalysts including the bulk nickel aluminate were further characterised by TEM from the measurement of the size of more than 250 particles. The corresponding histograms are included in Figure S1. The obtained mean size was 8 and 12 nm for NiAl-CZ and NiAl-CeO₂, respectively. When compared with XRD data it was reasonable to think that active nickel particles were small aggregates of crystallites. From the measured nickel crystallite size the dispersion and accessible metallic surface were calculated according to the methodology proposed by Borodziński and Bonarowska.²⁸ Results included in Table 1 evidenced that both nickel catalysts exhibited a similar available nickel surface, namely, 10 m² g⁻¹ for NiAl-CZ and 8 m² g⁻¹ for NiO-CeO₂.

As a brief summary of the characterisation of the catalytic samples it can be pointed out that the reduction of NiAl₂O₄ precursor deposited on both ceria-based supports leads to samples with a Ni particle size around 10 nm. Thus, the metallic dispersion was similar irrespective of the support. However, remarkable differences were noticed in the redox properties since the reducibility of CeO₂ was larger in spite of the fact that CeAlO₃ was also substantially formed as a result of the interaction between CeO₂ and Al₂O₃.

3.2. *Catalytic behaviour and characterisation of post-run samples*

The partial oxidation of methane over nickel catalysts occurs through an indirect two-step mechanism based on total oxidation at lower temperatures (< 650 °C) followed by methane reforming by CO₂ or steam at high temperatures (> 650 °C). For this reason the reforming efficiency of the NiAl- and NiO-based catalysts was examined at 700 °C. The reaction was performed with a stoichiometric O/C molar ratio (O/C=1) and a VHSV of 38400 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ during a relatively short time interval (3 h). For the sake of comparison the behaviour of the commercial rhodium catalyst and the bulk nickel

aluminate was also investigated. Previously the intrinsic activity of the Ni-free oxide supports was analysed under the same reaction conditions. Both bare samples were reduced at 850 °C for 2 h. It was found that conversion was lower than 12%. In view of the absence of H₂ and CO in the product stream, total combustion of methane took place exclusively (only CO₂ was detected). Virtually the same conversion level (14%) was achieved when the supports were only calcined at 850 °C with no subsequent high-temperature reduction. This finding suggested that the supports were easily oxidised when the reaction mixture was fed to the reactor. On account of these evidences the reforming activity of both CeO₂-based oxides could be considered negligible.^{29,30} Additional experiments with the freshly reduced supports were carried out when feeding a mixture of CH₄/N₂ keeping the same VHSV. No conversion of methane was noticed. These observations clearly evidenced that active oxygen species reacting with methane via total oxidation should be supplied from the gas-phase oxygen (in other words, the active sites Ce³⁺ should adsorbed oxygen immediately from the gas-phase oxygen to then release activated oxygen species reacting with methane). Judging from these results it could be a priori proposed that the positive role of Ce-based supports in the partial oxidation of methane, if any, would be to promote the reforming reactions with CO₂ and/or H₂O or to favour the gasification of the coke eventually formed during reaction.

Results plotted in Figure 6 evidenced a notably high conversion for both supported NiAl samples. In fact, the two samples gave a virtually identical conversion value of 72%, relatively close to the equilibrium value (86%). On the contrary, the supported NiO samples showed a considerably poorer performance with conversion values as low as 45% for NiO-CZ and 38% for NiO-CeO₂. It was then demonstrated that the selection of the Ni²⁺ precursor (nickel aluminate or nickel oxide) was crucial for producing active nickel

catalysts. Under identical thermal conditions selected for catalyst activation nickel aluminate was more suitable for achieving metallic nickel with a substantially smaller particle size (close to 10 nm, as determined by TEM). Furthermore, the catalysts derived from the NiAl_2O_4 precursor showed remarkably higher specific surface areas than those prepared from NiO, due to the contribution of the surface area provided by the alumina generated after the reduction pre-treatment.³¹ Indeed, the NiAl catalyst supported on CZ exhibited a specific surface area four times higher than the NiO-CZ counterpart sample (48 vs. $12 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Similarly, the NiAl catalyst supported on CeO_2 sample showed an area approximately ten times higher in comparison with that of the NiO- CeO_2 sample (48 vs. $5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). This higher surface area in turn led to a larger available nickel surface area, and consequently more active catalysts. The comparable metallic surface area found in both NiAl-CZ and NiAl- CeO_2 resulted in a very similar catalytic performance. Apparently the activity of the samples appeared not to be controlled by other factors such as the overall reducibility and/or the formation of CeAlO_3 . This similar behaviour of nickel catalysts supported on either ceria or ceria-zirconia mixed oxides with a low Ce/Zr molar ratio was consistent with previous works on the partial oxidation of methane with an O/C molar ratio close to one.^{32,33}

Figure 6

Finally, the comparison of the results obtained by the supported NiAl samples and those displayed by the bulk NiAl sample (with a noticeably higher nickel content, $X_{\text{CH}_4}=77\%$) and the commercial Rh- Al_2O_3 catalyst (widely recognised as one of the best catalyst for methane reforming, $X_{\text{CH}_4}=82\%$) pointed out that activity was only slightly lower. This evidenced the notable efficiency for this type of novel nickel supported catalysts. It is worth pointing out the fact that the available Ni surface of the freshly reduced bulk spinel was

about $17 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, somewhat higher than that of the supported NiAl samples ($8\text{-}10 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), thereby confirming that the activity of the three NiAl_2O_4 -based catalysts was only a function of the nickel surface area, at least when performing the reaction under stoichiometric conditions. On the other hand, it was obvious that the main advantage of the investigated supported NiAl catalysts was that the same performance was attained with a nickel content (14wt.%) lowered by more than half with respect to the bulk spinel (31wt.%). Unfortunately, since these activity data are obtained in an integral reactor with conversion levels in the 73-77% range it is not possible to calculate the corresponding TOF values of the NiAl-based catalysts.

As for product distribution no appreciable changes over the studied time span were noticed. Figure 6 includes the evolution of the yield of hydrogen with time on stream while Table S2 summarises the yields of CO and CO_2 and H_2/CO and CO/CO_2 molar ratios for the various nickel samples and the rhodium catalyst. The supported NiAl catalysts gave comparable yields of hydrogen (0.66-0.67), carbon monoxide (0.59-0.60) and carbon dioxide (0.13). As a result of their higher conversion, significantly larger yields to partial oxidation products were obtained over the bulk NiAl ($Y_{\text{H}_2}=0.73$ and $Y_{\text{CO}}=0.66$) and the Rh- Al_2O_3 ($Y_{\text{H}_2}=0.79$ and $Y_{\text{CO}}=0.72$) catalysts. These samples showed a lower selectivity to CO_2 , as revealed by the higher CO/CO_2 molar ratios (5.6 over NiAl and 6.8 over Rh- Al_2O_3). On the other hand, the supported NiO samples expectedly gave a much lower yield of hydrogen ($Y_{\text{H}_2}=0.24\text{-}0.32$). Last but not least, under the employed operational conditions there was no evidence of coking (as revealed by TGA-MS, not shown) and sintering of the nickel particles was negligible (as evidenced by XRD, not shown).

In order to determine if the composition of the ceria-based support could play a relevant role in optimising the behaviour of the resultant nickel catalysts, a new set of experiments

was carried out with the essential aim of inducing the formation of coke. For this purpose, the O/C molar ratio was lowered from 1 to 0.8, the volume hourly space velocity was increased from 38400 to 60000 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ and the reaction time interval was extended up to 30 h. Under these comparatively more severe conditions significant differences in behaviour would be a priori expected for the two investigated supported NiAl samples. Figure 7 shows the evolution of methane conversion and yield of hydrogen with time on stream. Data from the commercial rhodium catalyst and the bulk spinel were also included for the sake of comparison. It was thus undoubtedly observed that the most active catalysts were NiAl-CeO₂ and the bulk nickel aluminate, with an initial conversion (X_{CH_4} =66-67%) practically equal to that predicted by thermodynamics, and slightly higher than the reference rhodium catalyst (X_{CH_4} =63%). Besides, these samples exhibited a notable stability with no significant variation of conversion with time on line. In contrast, the NiAl-CZ catalyst exhibited a significantly lower initial conversion (X_{CH_4} =59%) with an evident loss of activity of about 7%. Accordingly, a similar trend was noticed when the yield of hydrogen was compared (Figure 7). Hence, the NiAl-CeO₂, NiAl and Rh-Al₂O₃ samples gave a stable, identical yield (Y_{H_2} =0.58), considerably larger than that achieved over the NiAl-CZ catalyst (Y_{H_2} =0.48, this value corresponded to the end of the experiment). On the other hand, as listed in Table S3, the H₂/CO molar ratios given by the NiAl-CeO₂ and NiAl catalysts were very similar (around 2.0) and the CO/CO₂ ratios were also comparable (close to 6.4), except for the NiAl-CZ sample, which achieved a significantly lower value (5.1, this value corresponded to the end of the experiment).

Figure 7

In order to gain insight into the markedly different behaviour of the two supported NiAl catalysts, the spent samples were thoroughly characterised by XRD, BET measurements,

TGA-MS, TEM and Raman spectroscopy. XRD analysis was helpful in characterising the state of the metallic phase and revealing the eventual presence of coke with a crystalline structure. The diffraction patterns (Figure S2) of the used samples evidenced, on one hand, the absence of NiO phase and on the other hand, the formation of graphitic carbon as the signal at $2\theta=26.6^\circ$ (JCPDS 89-8487) was clearly visible. Nevertheless, since the possible formation of amorphous carbon could not be detected by XRD, the post-reaction samples were additionally characterised by Raman spectroscopy (Figure S3). Two bands were observed; the first one (the so-called D band), at 1350 cm^{-1} , related to the structural imperfection of graphite and the second one (the so-called G band), at 1575 cm^{-1} , attributed to the in-plane carbon-carbon stretching vibrations of graphite layers.^{34,35} In addition, a shoulder band at 1610 cm^{-1} (denoted as D' band) was noticed, which is usually related to imperfect graphite or disordered carbons as well.³⁶ The ratio between the area of the D band and the area of the G band (I_D/I_G) can be regarded as an index for the crystalline order of graphite.^{35,36} Thus, the I_D/I_G value was calculated from curve fitting of each Raman spectrum using Lorentzian lines for these three bands (D, D' and G). It was found that both amorphous and graphitic filamentous carbon were present in the two supported NiAl catalysts with a similar distribution in view of their comparable I_D/I_G value, between 0.9 and 1.0 (Table 3).

Table 3

The samples were also analysed by TEM. Thus, the average particle size could be estimated from the measurement of about 80 particles. This was about 17 nm for NiAl-CeO₂ and 15 nm for NiAl-CZ (Table 3). Although a slight sintering was evident, the extent of this increase in particle size was relatively similar. Therefore it could be inferred that particle growth was not a key factor for explaining the clearly different catalytic behaviour of the

supported NiAl catalysts. It should be also remarked that the mean Ni particle size of the spent NiAl sample was 16 nm, very close to that measured for the supported catalysts.

On the other hand, the specific surface area of the spent samples considerably increased by a factor of 1.6 (from $48 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for the freshly reduced samples to $74\text{-}80 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) owing to the contribution of the porosity of the deposited carbon (Table 3).³⁷ The observed same extent for this increase suggested that the amount of carbonaceous deposits present in both samples should not be very different. Thus, the total amount of carbon deposited on the spent catalysts as well as the peak oxidation temperatures were determined by TGA-MS. Figure S4 shows the derivative thermal gravimetric change versus temperature. The combustion of coke occurred in the $450\text{-}720 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range. The oxidation profiles for both samples were characterised by a main broad peak at $605 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a shoulder at lower temperatures ($550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). These features correspond to the combustion to CO and preferentially CO_2 as suggested by the CO ($m/z=28$) and CO_2 ($m/z=44$) MS signals. Judging from these results it was suggested that deposited coke was filamentous carbon.³⁸ On the other hand, the significant presence of coating carbon (as CH_x carbonaceous species) was ruled out due to the absence of oxidation peaks accompanied by water formation below $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In fact, the H_2O ($m/z=18$) signal was flat in the whole temperature range. TEM images (Figure S5) further confirmed that the used catalysts were mainly covered with filamentous carbon. A close inspection of these carbonaceous structures indicated that they were bamboo-shaped carbon nanotubes with internal ducts forming hollow compartments, with diameters in the $10\text{-}30 \text{ nm}$ range and lengths near to 1 micron .^{39,40} Furthermore, being the shape of the cavity of the bamboo-like carbon quite similar to that of the metal at the tip suggested that the carbon grew around metal and at the

metal-carbon interface.⁴¹ Actually, metal particles were also seen inside the nanotubes, indicating the occurrence of the tip, rather than base growth mechanism.

As shown in Table 3 coke formation was larger for the NiAl-CZ sample (55%) compared with the CeO₂ supported catalyst (49%), thereby pointing out the role played the higher oxygen mobility of pure ceria with respect to the mixed oxide. Indeed, this beneficial effect was more evident when the deposition of coke was referred to converted methane over each catalyst during 30 h. Thus, this specific formation was 80 $\mu\text{mol C mol}_{\text{reacted CH}_4}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for NiAl-CZ whereas it was notably reduced for the NiAl-CeO₂ sample, namely 51 $\mu\text{mol C mol}_{\text{reacted CH}_4}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$. Moreover, the ability of the ceria-based sample for inducing coke deposition was also lower with respect to the bulk NiAl sample (71 $\mu\text{mol C mol}_{\text{reacted CH}_4}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$). As evidenced by Figure 7, the behaviour of the NiAl-CeO₂ catalyst was hardly affected by coking, thus suggesting that its larger reducibility was able to maintain the activity of nickel particles located at the tip of the nanotubes, probably by promoting the oxidation or gasification of the carbonaceous deposits in their vicinity.⁵ In this way the impact of filamentous carbon on the catalytic performance could be considered weak as nickel particles were not massively encapsulated, and therefore these remained accessible to reactants. The conversion maintenance in the presence of considerable amount of coke was consistent with the results obtained over a 10%Ni/15%CeO₂/Al₂O₃ catalyst in the dry reforming of methane.¹⁶ Conversely, the NiAl-CZ sample exhibited a poorer catalytic behaviour, with a lower conversion and a significant decay of both conversion and yield of hydrogen under severe reaction conditions. It was reasonable to expect that the lower reducibility of the mixed oxide in comparison with ceria was responsible for a less efficient removal of carbon on the active sites.

3.3. *Enhancement of the catalytic behaviour of the NiAl-CZ sample by La addition*

In an attempt to improve the catalytic behaviour of the low-ceria CZ mixed oxide investigated in this work, this oxide was modified with lanthanum (5wt.%La₂O₃) by impregnation prior to nickel incorporation. This amount was in a very close proportion to that required to form a theoretical monolayer of La₂O₃ (12.8 μmol La m⁻²) over the oxide surface. This oxide was denoted as LaCZ (La_{0.04}Ce_{0.13}Zr_{0.83}O₂, Mel Chemicals). The surface area was 30 m² g⁻¹, somewhat larger than its counterpart (24 m² g⁻¹). No diffraction peaks of La₂O₃ were detected in the XRD pattern, thereby suggesting that either the structure was amorphous or that La₂O₃ was highly dispersed on the mixed oxide. However, XPS of the La 3d_{5/2} core level spectra of the sample (Figure S6) clearly evidenced the presence of this promoter on the surface. Indeed, the position of the main peak at 835.0 eV and the characteristic distance between this main peak and its satellite of about 4 eV undoubtedly confirmed the existence of La₂O₃ on the surface of the catalyst. Although there was no enhancement of the overall reducibility (0.49 mmol H₂ g⁻¹ for both mixed oxides), the H₂ uptake (Figure 3) was observed to take place at lower temperatures (about 550 °C), which pointed out a significant improvement of the migration ability of oxygen anions with respect to the CZ oxide (625 °C).⁴²⁻⁴⁴

Nickel aluminate was incorporated by precipitation (13.4wt.%Ni) following the previously described synthesis route (NiAl-LaCZ). The deposition of the spinel was corroborated by both XRD and XPS. Characterisation results of this sample by BET measurements and H₂-TPR (Figure 4) did not reveal significant variations in comparison with the La-free nickel counterpart (NiAl-CZ). Hence, the surface area was also 48 m² g⁻¹ and the extent of the reducibility of the support was not improved by nickel (Table 2). TEM analysis revealed

that the average Ni particle size of the freshly reduced sample was around 11 nm, similar to that found for the NiAl-CZ sample (8 nm). Therefore the La addition did not involve a noticeable change in the available nickel surface area ($8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for NiAl-LaCZ and $10 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for NiAl-CZ).

Figure 7 shows the catalytic activity and yield of hydrogen at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a feed ratio of $\text{O/C}=0.8$ and a volume hourly space velocity of $60000 \text{ mL CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ during 30 h. It was noticed that activity was considerably enhanced with respect to the NiAl-CZ counterpart. In fact, the La-modified sample achieved an initial conversion ($X_{\text{CH}_4}=64\%$) close to that shown by NiAl-CeO₂. Accordingly, hydrogen yield was also improved ($Y_{\text{H}_2}=0.56$) compared with the NiAl-CZ sample ($Y_{\text{H}_2}=0.52$). However, a certain loss of activity (about 5%) and yield of hydrogen (around 7%) with time on stream was visible. Since La₂O₃ addition apparently had no marked effect on the surface area, nickel particle size and available metallic surface area, other catalytic properties were examined in order to explain the observed marked activity and better stability of the NiAl-LaCZ catalyst. Firstly, the impact of La₂O₃ on CeAlO₃ formation during the high-temperature reduction step prior to reaction was analysed. Thus, following the aforementioned procedure for quantifying the presence of this phase, it was found that the relative amount of Ce⁴⁺ irreversibly converted into CeAlO₃ decreased from 13% for NiAl-CZ to 8% for NiAl-LaCZ. On the basis of the fact that the lanthana layer was physically layered out between the mixed oxide and the alumina, the interaction between both structures was expected to diminish. In this way it was suggested that the affinity of Ce³⁺ ions from the mixed oxide for the alumina could be further weakened by the preferential formation of LaAlO₃ instead of CeAlO₃.⁴⁵ Consequently the redox properties of the support were slightly better preserved ($0.27 \text{ mmol H}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in comparison with $0.25 \text{ mmol H}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) (Table 2).

TEM analysis of the spent catalysts (Table 3) revealed an increase in particle size from 11 to 18 nm, which was comparable to that found for the La-free catalyst (from 8 to 15 nm). Therefore the addition of La_2O_3 did not avoid the sintering of the metallic sites. Certainly the main advantage of the presence of La_2O_3 was that the observed amount of coke was significantly reduced down to 45% that corresponded to $46 \mu\text{mol C mol}_{\text{reacted CH}_4}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ ($80 \mu\text{mol C mol}_{\text{reacted CH}_4}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the La-free sample). This finding was connected with the favoured adsorption of CO_2 which promoted the gasification of the carbonaceous deposits.⁴⁶ However, it must be pointed out that the combustion characteristics (with a main oxidation peak temperature at $620 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, as evidenced in Figure S4), morphology (filaments, as shown in Figure S5), and crystalline order (with a I_D/I_G ratio of 1.0, as revealed in Figure S3) were similar to those noticed for the La-free counterpart (Table 3). Therefore, the better behaviour of NiAl-LaCZ catalyst was attributed to the synergetic effects derived from La addition on the redox properties, partial inhibition of the CeAlO_3 formation and a less favoured formation of coke. As a result, notable improvements were achieved regarding both conversion and stability, with a limited deactivation with time on stream. The beneficial effects derived from the presence of La_2O_3 have been evidenced for the $\text{Ce}_{0.13}\text{Zr}_{0.87}\text{O}_2$ support but suggest that its addition to a pure ceria support with better redox properties could also induce a positive effect on the behaviour of a NiAl-LaCeO₂ catalyst. This is indeed the motivation for future research on the optimisation of NiAl₂O₄/Ce(Zr)O₂-type catalyst for the partial oxidation of methane.

Conclusions

Synthesized Ni/Ce(Zr)O₂ from NiAl₂O₄ precursor show interesting features for the partial oxidation of methane in comparison with their counterparts prepared from NiO. When oxygen is stoichiometrically fed to the reactor the observed activity is the same regardless

the support employed (pure CeO₂ or CZ mixed oxide). However, the good performance of these novel catalysts is particularly relevant when running under substoichiometric O/C conditions and high volume hourly space velocities. Although coke formation is considerable, a high and relatively stable behaviour is found owing to the fact that the redox properties of the ceria-based supports, specially those for CeO₂, help in maintaining the notable activity of the nickel crystallites derived from the spinelic precursor by removing carbonaceous species from their vicinity. La₂O₃ addition is useful for partially reducing the formation of inactive CeAlO₃ and minimising the negative effect of coking.

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Supporting Information

Experimental details of the characterisation techniques; Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ surface composition (Table S1); Performance of the catalysts under different reforming conditions (Tables S2 and S3); Particle size distribution (Figure S1); XRD patterns of the spent catalysts (Figure S2); Raman spectra of the spent catalysts (Figure S3); TGA-MS profiles of the spent catalysts (Figure S4); TEM images of the spent catalysts (Figure S5); XPS spectra of the NiAl-LaCZ catalyst (Figure S6).

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CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES

- Table 1 Physico-chemical characterisation of the supports and the reduced catalysts.
- Table 2 Redox properties of the investigated catalysts.
- Table 3 Properties of the used catalysts (reaction conditions: O/C=0.8; 60000 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 700 °C; 30 h).
- Figure 1 XRD patterns of bulk NiAl₂O₄ and NiO and supported NiAl and NiO catalysts: a) calcined and b) reduced samples.
- Figure 2 XPS spectra of Ni 2p_{3/2} region of supported NiAl and NiO catalysts.
- Figure 3 H₂-TPR profiles of the bare ceria-based supports and bulk NiO and NiAl₂O₄.
- Figure 4 H₂-TPR profiles of supported NiAl and NiO catalysts.
- Figure 5 XPS spectra of Ce 3d region of NiAl-CZ and NiAl-CeO₂ catalysts: a) calcined and b) reduced samples (light bands: Ce³⁺; dark bands: Ce⁴⁺).
- Figure 6 Evolution of methane conversion and yield of hydrogen as a function of time on stream over the examined catalysts (reaction conditions: O/C=1; 38400 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 700 °C; 3 h).
- Figure 7 Evolution of methane conversion and yield of hydrogen as a function of time on stream over the examined catalysts (reaction conditions: O/C=0.8; 60000 mL CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 700 °C; 30 h).

Table 1

Catalyst	Ni, wt.%	Ni Precursor	^a S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , mL g ⁻¹	d _p , Å	Ni ⁰ _{XRD} , nm	Ni ⁰ _{TEM} , nm	D, %	S _{Ni} , m ² g ⁻¹
CeO ₂	-	-	28	0.17	199	-	-	-	-
CZ	-	-	24	0.06	100	-	-	-	-
LaCZ	-	-	30	0.08	107	-	-	-	-
NiAl-CeO ₂	13.5	NiAl ₂ O ₄	48(54)	0.18	163	n.d.	12	11	8
NiAl-CZ	13.6	NiAl ₂ O ₄	48(52)	0.17	115	6	8	15	10
NiAl-LaCZ	13.4	NiAl ₂ O ₄	48(54)	0.20	147	13	11	11	8
NiO-CeO ₂	14.4	NiO	5(8)	0.01	394	102	-	-	-
NiO-CZ	14.4	NiO	12(12)	0.04	108	145	-	-	-
NiAl	30.9	NiAl ₂ O ₄	78(87)	0.30	118	9	12	10	17
Rh-Al ₂ O ₃	-	-	102(132)	0.42	99	-	-	-	-

^a Values in parentheses corresponded to the surface area of the calcined samples.

n.d.: not determined.

Table 2

Catalyst	Experimental H ₂ uptake, mmol g ⁻¹	Theoretical H ₂ uptake, mmol g ⁻¹		1st TPR		2nd TPR		(CeAlO ₃)
		U _{Ni} Ni ²⁺ →Ni ⁰	U _{Ce} Ce ⁴⁺ →Ce ³⁺	H ₂ uptake of the support, mmol g ⁻¹	^a Ce ³⁺ , %	H ₂ uptake of the support, mmol g ⁻¹	^b Ce ³⁺ , %	^c Ce ³⁺ , %
CeO ₂	1.63	-	2.91	1.63	56	-	-	-
CZ	0.49	-	0.49	0.49	100	-	-	-
LaCZ	0.49	-	0.49	0.49	100	-	-	-
NiAl-CeO ₂	3.33	2.30	1.72	1.03	60	0.66	38	35
NiAl-CZ	2.61	2.32	0.29	0.29	100	0.25	87	13
NiAl-LaCZ	2.58	2.28	0.29	0.29	100	0.27	92	8
NiO-CeO ₂	3.13	2.49	2.37	0.64	27	-	-	-
NiO-CZ	2.67	2.45	0.40	0.22	54	-	-	-

^a Ce³⁺ (%) = (U_{TPR} - U_{Ni}) / U_{Ce}, in which U_{TPR}, U_{Ni} and U_{Ce} represent the experimental H₂ uptake in the TPR experiment, the theoretical H₂ uptake for reduction of Ni²⁺ (to Ni⁰) and the theoretical H₂ uptake for reduction of Ce⁴⁺ (to Ce³⁺), respectively. It is assumed that, besides the reduction of Ni, H₂ uptake is only consumed for the following reactions: 2CeO₂+H₂→Ce₂O₃+H₂O and 2CeO₂+Al₂O₃+H₂→2CeAlO₃+H₂O. Data corresponded to a single H₂-TPR (950 °C) run.

^b Ce³⁺ (%) values determined after a successive H₂-TPR/O₂-TPO/H₂-TPR cycle.

^c Ce³⁺ (%) values corresponded to Ce⁴⁺ fixed as CeAlO₃.

Table 3

Catalyst	$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$\text{Ni}^0_{\text{TEM}}, \text{nm}$	Coke, %	$\mu\text{mol C mol}_{\text{reacted CH}_4}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	$I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$
NiAl-CeO ₂	76	17	49	51	0.9
NiAl-CZ	80	15	55	80	1.0
NiAl-LaCZ	77	18	45	46	1.0
NiAl	74	16	57	71	0.8
Rh-Al ₂ O ₃	125	-	1	1	-

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7